

Validation of Customer Requirements by System Simulation Taking Tolerances and System Variations into Account

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Abstract

The aim of the following contribution is to introduce an integrated process which allows the implementation of factors that have a significant impact on the limiting positions. These limiting positions and their effects on geometric deviations and displacements need to be investigated in order to ensure that functional aspects of an assembly are fulfilled for large quantities.

The presented approach involves the finding of these limiting positions using statistical methods and state-of-the-art tools as well as the simulation of the flexible and compliant components. It will be illustrated in connection with the environment of a modern vehicle entry. A simplified section of the geometry is used to explain the planned procedure.

The proposed process is divided into three major steps. The first step includes the implementation of a rigid tolerance simulation, which delivers information about probability distributions in order to determine the limiting positions. Second, a finite element analysis (FEA) of the door sealing system under geometric deviations in accordance to the results of the 3DCS simulation (state-of-the-art tolerance analysis tool implemented in CATIA V5) is performed. Third, a FEA of the door and the side frame, providing corresponding deformation data, leads to the limiting positions with regard to the elastic system behaviour.

Finally, this process enables the user to evaluate the system behaviour of a door assembly with respect to the limiting positions in more detail.

1. Introduction

From a company's point of view it is important to ensure that functional, as well as visual requirements of a product are fulfilled in series production. It is important to ensure that customer requirements are met for large quantities. Tolerance management and robust design methodologies are useful tools to grant this.

In the following piece of work an automotive door assembly will be examined. The focus of all activities will be on customer-relevant functional aspects. From the customer's perspec-

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tive, one of the most relevant attributes is tightness. In order to build a proper design, it is the aim to make sure that the observed system guarantees tightness against the permeation of dust or humidity such as rain and condensation. Similar to aspects like the handling comfort, opening forces, aerodynamics, etc., the sealing system is affected by the limiting positions of the observed assembly. These limiting positions are mainly influenced by functional relevant components, which themselves have nominal dimensions on the one hand and corresponding geometric deviations on the other. In particular, the main components that belong to this assembly are the side frame, the door sealing system and the door inner panel (body in white, see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic of the contributors belonging to the assembly

In the assembly process it becomes clear that all statistical deviations belonging to these single contributors will be chained together. This combination leads to the limiting positions in the end and in general can be seen as the largest deviations from the nominal dimensions that can occur (Kapici et al, 2013).

These limiting positions are of crucial importance for the functional, as well as robust construction and the corresponding validation. They can appear as a result of the production process, purchased parts, the assembly process and the system behaviour. Optionally, they should be located within the tolerance specifications (requirements set by the designer), which is not always the case at present.

The question therefore, is how to ensure these functional criteria of a product at an early stage if there is no hardware available. The use of stochastic simulations, in particular tolerance analysis, is considered a suitable approach.

The objective of this contribution therefore, is to introduce an integrated process which allows to take into account all deviations that have a significant impact on the limiting positions. These are geometric deviations as well as reaction forces which result in geometric deformations and displacements. This specifically developed methodology will be examined due to the fact that there is no other available.

First a determination of the limiting positions by using a rigid tolerance simulation is presented. It is used as a reference result. It will be used to show the advantages of taking into account the system behaviour (geometric deviations and displacements). Afterwards the sealing system will be investigated under geometric deviations. As a result both of the rigid tolerance simulation and the elastic behaviour of the sealing system the determination of the limiting positions is performed and outlined.

2. Determination of the limiting positions by using a rigid tolerance simulation

As previously stated, the process of developing the limiting positions (rigid) of the considered automotive door assembly is the first part. In this case, it consists of the side frame, the sealing system and the door inner panel (see Figure 1). Therefore, a CAD data set containing the

geometry data, as well as deviation information from all contributors, needs to be available. Once all of the information is received, the rigid tolerance simulation can be performed using the state-of-the-art tolerance analysis tool 3DCS Analyst (3DCS). The latter is integrated into CATIA V5 as chargeable application. In the following a step-by-step guide is introduced to achieve these rigid limiting positions.

Step one, the mounting process needs to be implemented. Within this step, all parts involved in the process will be determined. Additionally, their mounting sequence and their adjustment concept are of great importance and need to be considered in order to reduce their six degrees of freedom. In Figure 2 a suitable approach is outlined regarding the mounting process. In this step, the mounting sequence is separated into two main parts:

- Figure 2 i) Positioning of the door inner panel on the workpiece carrier with regard to the alignment concept.
- Figure 2 ii) & iii) Positioning of the workpiece carrier along the side frame using adjustment points on the side frame.
- Note: The alignment concept is represented using circles that include respective axis directions showing the way one part is oriented on the other one.

Figure 2. Illustration of one valid mounting sequence: i) Application of the door inner panel on the workpiece carrier ii) & iii) Positioning of the workpiece carrier along the side frame (Epple, 2013)

Input: single parts, workpiece carrier and mounting sequence
Output: the mounting process of the assembly is mapped virtually

The second step deals with the insertation of permissible dimensional deviations. These are integrated in the simulation via component tolerances as well as mounting tolerances.

Input: permissible dimensional deviation
Output: in addition, the simulation contains component tolerances and mounting tolerances

The positions of the measurement points are set in **the third step**. For the present case, this means that there are five positions determined empirically (X1Y1, X2Y3, X3Y4, Y2Z1, Y5Z2), each containing two measurements of key product characteristics (KPCs) in X and Y direction or in Y and Z direction. These KPCs are critical design features that monitor the relative position between several components in order to improve product quality (Ceglarek et al, 2004). As can be seen from Figure 3, there are three measurements having their largest part in X direction. Furthermore, one can recognize that there are five measurements in Y direction and two measurements in Z direction. In this case, and in order to capture door-sided tilting, two measurements are performed along the B-pillar.

Figure 3. Illustration of the coordinate plane and measurement points between side frame and door inner panel (Epple, 2013)

Input: (empirical) knowledge

Output: the positions of the measurement points are set

In **step four**, the actual CATIA 3DCS simulation is carried out with the goal of building a virtual tolerance model. Dimensional deviations that have been defined up to this point will now be varied within their respective tolerance range. These variations will be carried out by the use of the Monte-Carlo-method that generates uniformly distributed random numbers, which themselves, will be transformed into predefined distributions. (Rubinstein, 1981, VDI, 1999) The virtual assembly follows as soon as all of the various deviations are charged with random numbers arising from these distributions. In the next step, the key product characteristics (KPC) are measured and stored. This step is repeated until the required sample size is reached. Thus, every measurement at every examined position contains just as much related key product characteristics.

Input: dimensional deviations are getting varied within their respective tolerance range in order to build a virtual tolerance model using CATIA 3DCS

Output: deviations (statistical information about local key product characteristics) at the measurement point

In **the fifth step**, the registered data is statistically evaluated in order to be able to determine the rigid limiting positions. That evaluation can be performed using both CATIA 3DCS and other software solutions. As previously specified, as a result of these examinations, the limiting positions, (see Table 1) as well as a corresponding contributor analysis, arise. This analysis shows the impact of every dimensional deviation on the key product characteristic. As stated in (Epple, 2013), from the user's point of view it is important to ensure these key product characteristics. Two different cases can be distinguished in the general proceeding. First, if the key product characteristics can be achieved, the tightest tolerances should be relaxed to reduce manufacturing costs. Second, if the key product characteristics can't be achieved, the contributor(s) with the largest impact on these characteristics need(s) to be reduced in order to solve this problem.

Table 1. Illustration of possible key product characteristics (KPC), standard deviations (S), lower and upper specification limits (LSL, USL) corresponding to the measurement points

	X_1	X_2	X_3	Y_1	Y_2	Y_3	Y_4	Y_5	Z_1	Z_2
KPC	15,16	17,35	13,47	26,61	29,00	29,00	21,97	16,04	15,00	13,64
S	0,42	0,40	0,40	0,31	0,31	0,31	0,40	0,40	0,32	0,31
LSL	13,17	15,47	11,59	25,11	27,51	27,51	20,07	14,13	13,51	12,16
USL	17,16	19,23	15,35	28,10	30,49	30,49	23,87	17,95	16,50	15,12

in mm

Input: deviations at the measurement points

Output: rigid limiting positions at the measurement points

3. The role of the sealing system under geometric deviations

The limiting positions that have an impact on functional requirements are not only founded on dimensional deviations arising from the rigid body in white, but from the door sealing system influences with its geometric deviations, stiffness conditions and corresponding reaction forces as well. Additionally, the process of closing and some other factors also have an impact.

A 2D finite element analysis (FEA) is realised in order to show the effect on the limiting positions of the sealing system under geometric deviations. Therefore, a uniaxial translation motion of the door inner panel towards the side frame is performed. For this purpose, both the nominal position as well as the limiting positions will be examined closely. The goal for each case is to supply counter-pressure information as well as deformation data. The geometries of the side frame and the door inner panel are not resiliently modelled. In summary, there are 30 2D FEA relevant for the case considered (10 measurement points, each having the 3 positions nominal, upper limiting position, lower limiting position). In this case, the procedure of a finite element analysis follows the classical model which can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. General procedure of a FE simulation

In the pre-processing stage of the 2D FE simulation, the 2D planar sections of interest need to be extracted from the 3D CAD data set (in this case: CATIA). Afterwards, the data needs to be transferred to the finite element software. It should be noted that an individual should ensure that the component's location and orientation are properly transferred during this procedure. Inside the software, the model building process takes place, concerning the FE simulation. Non-linear contact problems like this are characterised by different modelling parameters. Some of these modelling parameters that have an impact on the results of a simulation are as follows:

- Material models and the specification of all material parameters included,
- Specification of all contact conditions including multilateral relations between different components, friction coefficients and the self contact of the door sealing system,

- Relative displacement distances between the components,
- Relative position of the moving components to each other,
- Limitation of the degrees of freedom of all considered components (boundary conditions),
- Kind of meshing and meshing quality.

Taking these parameters into account, a 2D finite element simulation result occurs. In accordance to the respective 2D planar sections the reaction forces, calculated within this simulation, arise.

Thereafter, in the **processing** step the actual 2D FE simulation is carried out taking the modelling and boundary conditions into consideration.

Consecutively, the **post-processing** in connection with the 2D FE simulation is conducted. This step deals with the visualization of the results as well with their interpretation. The suggested process takes the counter-pressure information arising from the sealing system as well as its respective reaction forces F_R into consideration. These factors are of crucial importance (see Figure 4). The reaction forces when performing the 3D FE simulation are applied to the side frame and the door inner panel - quasi static. In preparation for this aspect of the next stage, the transformation of the 2D reaction forces into the global 3D coordinate system must be executed in order to do an interpolation of these reaction forces along the sealing line. Figure 5 shows a schematic sample of interpolated data. In order to receive a reasonable result of interpolation it is necessary to produce more 2D FE simulations creating supporting points. At this point In order to understand the suggested process, this isn't necessary. In the end, this approach will lead to a more realistic result for the considered reaction forces based on the limiting positions along the sealing line.

Figure 5. Reaction Forces F_R as a result of the counter-pressure: i) Single reaction forces resulting from the 2D planar sections ii) Linear Interpolation of the reaction forces along the sealing line s

Due to the fact that the limiting positions are interdependent, mostly because of geometric boundary conditions, and to ensure that all positions are considered during the process, simulation series need to be carried out. In an attempt to limit the computation time a design of experiments needs to be conducted.

4. Determination of the limiting positions as a result both of the rigid tolerance simulation and the elastic behaviour of the sealing system

Following both phases of simulation, the determination of the elastic limiting positions is carried out. Therefore, the counter-pressure information (see Figure 5 i)), which arise from the sealing system and its respective limiting positions, are stamped on the side frame and the

door inner panel. This is done within a quasi-static 3D FE simulation. The aim is to determine the corresponding deformations with respect to the imprinted loads. As a consequence, the updated limiting positions occur due to this linear superposition.

To achieve these objectives, the components, namely door inner panel and side frame, are fixed at their dedicated connection points. In this case, this is carried out via door-sided connections at both hinges and at the door lock. The simulation process during this process step changes insofar as the loads are now imprinted along the sealing line.

The simulation's outcome provides the effect of the sealing system on the resulting limiting positions. The influence is clearly noticeable at several areas within this automotive door assembly. For the most part, these areas have a relatively low structural rigidity or are situated relatively far from the connection points (door hinge and door lock). An example of one of these areas is the door-sided upper corner near the B-pillar of the vehicle. Additional influences can be seen in places where the gasket is situated opposite of edges. There can be specific situations, maybe limiting positions, where the contact surface between the gasket and the body in white reaches a certain minimum or no longer exists. In this case, the customer-relevant criterion tightness (against the permeation of dust or humidity) can be evaluated directly from the simulation.

Furthermore, the result of an overall limiting position simulation can be that the gasket cannot be kept from reaching a point of being solidified. If this happens, this does not ensure the sealing of the system a priori. On the contrary, it might also happen that the sealing layer loses its sealing capabilities due to folding. Moreover, such behaviour may end up damaging the sealing profile over the short or medium term. This may cause a negative effect on the considered functional aspect. Here, it should be noted that follow-up research studies are required.

5. Summary and outlook

The process which has been introduced in this contribution supports the ambition of a customer-oriented functional safeguarding of the tightness criterion in an early stage of the developmental cycle of an automotive door assembly. The primary motivation behind the results from various overarching objectives are as follows: An increasing quality of the results required when predicting the limiting positions, as well as, an improved design construction in order to avoid functional errors. In this context, one of the most relevant attributes is examined, concerning tightness against the permeation of dust or humidity.

On the basis of three process steps, the reasons for dimensional, as well as for position deviations, were discussed. Furthermore, stiffness conditions of the components, the restorative forces set up, etc. are causative for the so called limiting position formation. Designated process steps should be the determination of the limiting positions by rigid tolerance simulation, a finite element analysis (FEA) of the door sealing system under geometric deviation and a FEA of the corresponding deformation to finally determine the limiting positions with regard to the elastic system behaviour.

The results achieved indicate that a useful process is determined. Nevertheless, especially in the area of finite element simulations, the need for further action arises. In order to detail the proposed process through additional information, the following points will be considered: Quality of the results, required computational time, costs incurred. To improve the quality of the simulation results, there will be follow-up research activities in the future. On the one hand, these studies should provide additional insights with respect to the location and number of the regarded 2D sections. On the other hand, the quality of the results coming from 3D FE simu-

lations should be examined. Finally, aims of these studies are to allow a comparison between 2D and 3D FE simulation and their respective results.

An additional step involving the opening and the closing of the door should be taken into account, and the effect of the sealing characteristics on the limiting positions and its corresponding key product characteristics should be illustrated more precisely.

In order to verify the quality of the simulation results, it is also useful to do comparative experiments. Therefore, an adequate design of experiments is required helping to reduce both the amount of simulations and experiments. Subsequently, it is the task to define a criterion which provides a good indication of the sealing capability. There are several options here: Numerically determined counter pressure information as well as the size of the contact surface of the gasket on the opposite component.

Finally, this process enables the user to evaluate the system behaviour of a door assembly with respect to the limiting positions in more detail. Thus, this simulation approach enables a more sustainable way of manufacturing which leads to a robust design in the end. Therefore, it serves the customer's, as well as the company's needs.

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